

The irrigation and date of transplanting interaction had a significant effect on rice yield both years (see table). The average reduction in early rice yield with irrigation 2 d after water infiltration was more than 1 t/ha; irrigation schedule had no effect on late rice.

The yield reduction was due to the interactive effect of irrigation and date of transplanting on tillering. Number of effective tillers/five plants in early rice decreased from 47 with continuous irrigation to 42 with irrigation 2 d after water infiltration.

Irrigation 2 d after water infiltration saved 65 cm irrigation water in 1982 and 33 cm in 1983. Lower water savings in 1983 were due to 67 cm rainfall during the crop

Interactive effect of irrigation schedule^a and date of transplanting on rice yield. Ludhiana, India, 1982-83.

Transplanting date	Yield (t/ha)								
	1982			1983			Mean		
	1 d	2 d	Mean	1 d	2 d	Mean	1 d	2 d	Mean
20 Jun	9.1	7.6	8.4	7.8	7.1	7.5	8.5	7.4	7.9
5 Jul	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.1	7.0	7.1	7.4	7.4	7.4
Mean	8.4	7.7		7.5	7.1		8.0	7.4	
LSD (P=0.05)									
I/D ^b	0.4				0.3			0.4	
I × D	0.8				0.4			0.5	

^a 1 d = daily irrigation, 2 d = irrigation 2 days after drainage of ponded water. ^b I = irrigation schedule, D = transplanting date.

season, compared to 38 cm rainfall during the 1982 crop season. Less than normal rain fell in Aug and no rain fell Sep-Oct.

Increased N also increased yield 0.6 t/ha. The N and irrigation and N and transplanting date interactions were not significant. □

Effect of seed treatment on crop stand of direct seeded rice

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We studied the effect of seed treatment on rice seedling emergence and on stand establishment with direct seeding in flooded and saturated soil. Four experiments under greenhouse and field conditions were conducted on alluvial sandy loam soil of Mahanadi delta (pH 6.2, 0.83% organic C, 12 mg available P/kg soil, and 65 mg available K/kg soil).

Seedling emergence was lower in flooded soils than in saturated soils. Seedling emergence was significantly higher when seeds were soaked in 0.1% KMnO₄ and water and coated with gypsum + ferric phosphate (Table 1). Seedling emergence with seeds treated with cow dung + soil was very low, particularly under flooded conditions. Seeds coated with gypsum or soaked with 0.3% H₂O₂ also had lower seedling emergence.

In general, seedling height was greater with direct seeding in flooded soils. Seedlings from seeds treated with cow dung + soil were less vigorous. In

Table 1. Effect of seed treatment on seedling emergence and plant height at 13 d after sowing. Cuttack, India, 1985 wet season.

Treatment	Seedling emergency ^a (no./tray)			Plant height (cm)		
	Flooded soil	Saturated soil	Mean	Flooded soil	Saturated soil	Mean
Variety						
Sabita (NC492)	51.8	61.4	56.6	38.2	21.8	30.0
FR13A	46.2	62.4	54.3	35.7	26.1	30.9
Utkal Prabha (CR1030)	42.3	56.9	49.6	33.3	19.0	26.2
Seed treatment						
Dry seed	46.8	59.7	53.3	33.4	24.5	29.0
Seeds soaked 48 h						
0.3% H ₂ O ₂	36.2	53.2	44.7	37.6	28.2	32.9
0.1% KMnO ₄	61.5	74.8	68.2	36.6	31.0	33.8
Water	66.0	69.8	67.9	40.4	27.6	34.0
Seed pellets ^b with						
4 g gypsum	45.7	55.7	50.7	35.8	22.0	28.9
4 g gypsum + 1 g ferric phosphate	56.3	65.7	61.0	37.0	25.6	31.3
8 g cow dung + soil	14.8	44.5	29.7	29.4	14.0	21.7
Mean	46.8	60.2		35.7	22.3	
LSD (0.05)						
Varieties		ns			ns	
Seed treatments		8.2			3.2	
Seeding method		5.4			1.5	
Varieties × seed treatments		ns			5.6	
Seed treatments × seeding method		8.8			ns	

^a 100 seeds/tray containing 12 kg soil; 10 cm standing water or saturated. ^b 10 seeds/pellet.

1987, seedling emergence, plant height, and plant dry weight were similar when seeds were soaked in water, 0.01% KMnO₄, or 0.3% H₂O₂ and sown in standing water; they were superior to plants from dry seeding (Table 2). The

higher seedling emergence in some treatments might be due to greater availability of oxygen during germination. Soil O₂ level drops to near zero within 24 h of submergence, while rice seedling demand for O₂ by

Table 2. Effect of seed treatment on crop stand of rice varieties (>14 DAS) sown in standing water.^a Cuttack, India, 1987 dry season.

Treatment	Seedling emergence (no./m ²)	Stand establishment (%)	Plant height (cm)	Dry weight/plant (g)
Variety				
Utkal Prabha	206	52	26	26
Kalinga 3	185	46	26	24
Ratna	171	43	25	25
LSD (0.05)	ns		ns	ns
Seed treatment				
Dry seed	144	36	24	18
Seeds soaked 48 h				
0.3% H ₂ O ₂	200	50	27	30
0.1% KMnO ₄	200	50	27	25
Water	205	51	26	26
LSD (0.05)	22		1.5	3

^a400 seeds sown/1-m² plot in 10 cm standing water; water depth 10 ± 2 cm.

rice seedlings increases greatly 2-3 d after germination.

Among the varieties tested, Sabita

showed comparatively higher emergence, followed by FR13A and

Utkal Prabha. □

Soil fertility and fertilizer management

Response of direct-sown rice to *Azospirillum lipoferum*

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We tested the effect of *A. lipoferum* on direct-sown rice during the Sep-Jan 1989 wet season.

Peat-based *A. lipoferum* inoculum at 2 kg/ha was mixed with 100 kg of IR20 seeds, using rice gruel water as sticker. The mixture was dried in the shade for 20 min, then sown. Peat-based inoculum at 4 kg/ha was mixed with 15 kg well-powdered farmyard

manure, broadcast, and covered with soil.

Four treatments were laid out in a random block design with five replications (see table). Experimental plots of 20 m² received 75 kg N/ha as urea in 3 splits (50% at 30 d after sowing (DAS), 25% at 60 DAS, and 25% at 90 DAS), 37.5 kg P/ha as superphosphate, and 37.5 kg K/ha as muriate of potash, both basal.

A. lipoferum applied through both seed and soil gave the highest grain and straw yields. Root weight, plant height, and productive tillers increased. □

Effect of *A. lipoferum* on direct sown rice. Aduthurai, India, 1989 wet season.

<i>Azospirillum</i> treatment	Plant height (cm)	Productive tillers (no./hill)	Root weight (g/hill)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)
Seed	69.7	7.7	1.51	2.4	3.2
Soil	67.5	7.6	1.76	2.3	2.8
Seed + soil	73.1	8.8	2.09	3.0	4.0
Control (no treatment)	67.4	7.5	1.45	2.3	2.9
LSD (P = 0.05)	5.5	0.6	0.17	0.53	0.90

Effect of zinc fertilizers on rice grown on Typic Ustochrepts

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We studied the efficiency of ZnSO₄ and Zn-EDTA applied in soil (11.2, 5.6, and 2.8 kg Zn/ha) and as foliar spray (0.02, 0.1, and 0.2% Zn solution) in long-duration PR106 grown on Typic Ustochrepts during 1988 wet season (kharif).

Soil was loamy sand with pH 8.5, electrical conductivity 0.32 dS/m, 0.42% organic C, and 0.50 mg DTPA extractable Zn/kg soil. Urea, diammonium phosphate, and muriate of potash were applied at 120-27-24 kg NPK/ha.

In the soil treatments, Zn was broadcast at transplanting (45-d-old seedlings). In the foliar spray treatments, the first spray was at 4 wk after transplanting and the remaining two at 10-d intervals. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Straw and grain samples were analyzed for Zn content.

Grain yield increased significantly with increasing rates of soil-applied Zn for both sources (see table). Foliar sprays of Zn-EDTA (except at 0.02% solution) and ZnSO₄ significantly

Effect of application methods, rates, and sources of Zn on rice yield and Zn uptake. Ludhiana, India, 1988 wet season.

Zn source	Zn rate	Yield (t/ha)		Zn uptake (g/ha)
		Grain	Straw	
<i>Soil application (kg Zn/ha)</i>				
ZnSO ₄ · 7H ₂ O	11.2	7.1	15.2	351
	5.6	6.6	14.4	283
	2.8	6.1	12.7	225
Zn-EDTA	11.2	7.6	15.9	378
	5.6	6.9	14.8	304
	2.8	6.3	13.5	240
<i>Foliar application (%)</i>				
ZnSO ₄ · 7H ₂ O	0.20	6.2	11.8	206
	0.10	5.9	10.1	164
Zn-EDTA	0.10	6.0	10.7	208
	0.02	5.7	8.2	144
Control		5.3	8.2	123
LSD (P = 0.05)		0.5	1.3	43